

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND SPIRITUALITY AS PREDICTORS OF HAPPINESS AMONG PUBLIC JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN SECOND CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT, BOHOL

Zendy T. Toston

Campao Oriental High School, Getafe, Bohol, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' happiness affects the classroom climate when they welcome students with warmth and consequently wipe out traces of fear and faltering. To get a closer sense of what causes teachers' happiness, this study evaluated the different teacher profiles and further assessed which of the said profiles can predict a teacher's happiness. Quantitative descriptive method was employed to identify the 541 Junior High School teachers of the Second Congressional District of Bohol as respondents of the study with 1415 population. A self-made questionnaire to capture teachers' profiles and the standardized Delaney Spiritual Scale and Oxford Happiness Survey was used as a data-gathering tool. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and multiple regression were used as statistical treatments. The surveyed respondents were mostly married females aged 26-30 years old. They were living with their immediate families with at most one child or dependent. Most of them earn ₱ 20,179.00 – ₱ 24,000.00 per month with a net take-home pay of ₱ 5,000.00 - ₱ 9,999.00 because of monthly deductions and other liabilities. Since they are mostly married, they have one other income source which is their husband's allotments. The teachers claimed to have no chronic or serious illnesses. When the study was conducted, most of them were taking their master's studies. They were mostly holding Teacher I posts with at least two ancillary designations and had been in service for 3 – 7 years. Most of them had not yet received any work and non-work-related recognitions. They were mostly not involved in civic and religious organizations, religious/ spiritual activities and were not holding roles in the local church. Lastly, these teachers were found to have a very high state of spirituality. The study concludes that happier teachers are those with longer teaching experience and with higher spirituality. Furthermore, a teacher tends to be happier if he/she is living with his/her immediate

family. Lastly, the study also concludes that teachers seem to be less happy as they advance in age.

Keywords: *Happiness, spirituality, secondary schools, Second Congressional District, Bohol, Philippines.*

INTRODUCTION

Happiness is a fundamental pursuit in human life, encompassing all aspects from personal well-being at home to professional satisfaction in the workplace. In the context of employment, particularly within educational institutions, the well-being of teachers is crucial. Beyond fair compensation, educators deserve a work environment that fosters their happiness, allowing them to fulfill their duties harmoniously. The notion that happiness breeds success is well-supported, especially in teaching, where a teacher's positive emotional state can significantly influence the classroom climate and, consequently, student achievement (Muijs & Reynolds, 2005; Entwistle, 1987).

However, the demands placed on teachers, both professionally and personally, raise concerns about their ability to maintain the happiness necessary to remain effective in their roles. Teacher status, a key factor in job satisfaction, is directly linked to outcomes such as job performance and emotional well-being (Schleicher, 2017). Recognizing the critical role of happiness in teaching, this study seeks to explore the factors that contribute to teachers' happiness, with the aim of understanding how these elements impact their professional efficacy and overall job satisfaction.

Recent research underscores the complexity of teacher well-being, emphasizing the need for a supportive work environment that promotes resilience and prevents burnout (Day & Gu, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). Teachers' relatedness with students, their sense of self-efficacy, and their engagement at work are crucial components of their overall happiness and job satisfaction (Collie et al., 2016). Moreover, the decision to remain in or leave the teaching profession is heavily influenced by the emotional and psychological support teachers receive, both from their peers and the institutions they work for (Kelchtermans, 2017).

Research has also shown that teachers' work engagement is closely linked to their motivation and the prevention of burnout, highlighting the importance of job characteristics and transformational leadership in fostering a positive work environment (Taris, Ybema, & van Beek, 2017). For instance, Fernet et al. (2015) demonstrated that transformational leadership plays a critical role in enhancing teachers' optimal functioning at work by improving their perceived job characteristics and intrinsic motivation.

The growing interest in the study of happiness, particularly within the educational sector, reflects a broader recognition of its importance in achieving institutional success. Happiness among teachers not only enhances their performance but also contributes to the creation of a positive and productive learning environment for students. This study is

anchored in the Objective List Theory and Desire Theory (Griffin, 1986), which provide frameworks for understanding the multifaceted nature of happiness. According to the Objective List Theory, happiness is derived from the achievement of objectively valuable life pursuits, such as career accomplishments, education, and interpersonal relationships. Meanwhile, Desire Theory posits that happiness is a result of fulfilling personal desires, regardless of the pleasure or displeasure associated with them.

In the context of education, the happiness of teachers is further supported by legal frameworks such as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (R.A. No. 4670) and the 1987 Philippine Constitution, which emphasize the importance of improving the social and economic status of teachers to attract and retain talent in the profession. These laws highlight the need for educational institutions to prioritize the well-being of their workforce, ensuring that teachers are not only compensated fairly but also provided with the necessary support to thrive both personally and professionally.

Given the increasing recognition of happiness as a key indicator of well-being, this study aims to assess the happiness levels of teachers and identify the personal and professional factors that significantly influence their happiness. By understanding these factors, educational institutions can better support their teachers, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes for students and a more positive school environment.

Research Questions

The study primarily aimed to evaluate the demographic profile of the public school teachers of the Second Congressional District of Bohol and further assess whether such profiles are predictors of their happiness.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 family structure/type;
 - 1.5 number of children;
 - 1.6 number of dependents;
 - 1.7 gross monthly salary;
 - 1.8 net take home pay;
 - 1.9 other sources of income;
 - 1.10 liabilities;
 - 1.11 health status;
 - 1.11.1 serious illness;
 - 1.11.2 chronic diseases?
 - 1.12 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.13 number of years in service;
 - 1.14 present rank;
 - 1.15 ancillary designations;

- 1.16 involvement in civic organizations;
 - 1.17 work-related recognitions;
 - 1.18 non-work related recognitions;
 - 1.19 involvement in religious organizations;
 - 1.2.1 involvement in religious/spiritual activities;
 - 1.2.2 involvement or role in the local church? and,
 - 1.20 state of spirituality?
2. What is the teachers' degree of happiness?
 3. Is teacher profile a significant predictor of happiness?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To achieve the purpose of this study, a descriptive survey design was employed. The comprehensive socio-demographic profiles of the teachers, collected through survey questionnaires, were statistically analyzed alongside their happiness scores, which were obtained using the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire. This approach was used to gather and analyze the necessary data for the study.

Research Environment

This study was conducted during the school year 2018-2019 in the 2nd District of Bohol, focusing on junior high school teachers as the chosen respondents. The 2nd District of Bohol consists of fourteen municipalities: Bien Unido, Buenavista, Clarin, Dagohoy, Danao, Getafe, Inabanga, Pres. Carlos P. Garcia, Sagbayan, San Isidro, San Miguel, Talibon, Trinidad, and Ubay.

Research Participants

In selecting the research respondents, a cluster sampling method was employed. Schools were randomly selected, followed by a complete enumeration of the junior high schools within the Second Congressional District of Bohol. Out of 72 schools, 26 were chosen as samples.

Table 1. Distribution of Participants

Name of School	Number of Teachers
Cabul-an National High School	14
Cangawa National High School	36
Lubang National High School	12
Panghagban National High School	16

Clarín National School of Fisheries	19
Nahawan National High School	11
Handumon National High School	16
Pandanon National High School	10
Tulang National High School	30
Inabanga High School	45
Inabanga North Central Integrated School	10
Southern Inabanga High School	34
Bugang National High School	16
Mahayag National High School	36
San Miguel Technical Vocational School	36
President Carlos P. Garcia Memorial High School	35
San Isidro High School	19
Sto. Niño High School	15
Sikatuna Nat'l Agricultural High School	10
Ponciana E. Leoligao High School	15
Zosimo A. Gulle Memorial National High School	22
Hinlayagan National High School	10
Kinan-oan High School	15
Tagum Sur National High School	25
Camambugan National High School	20
Bulilis National High School	14
Total	541

Research Instrument

The researcher used a self-developed questionnaire to collect data from teachers regarding their profile, state of spirituality, and degree of happiness. The questionnaire is divided into three sections. The first section gathers information on teachers' socio-economic and professional profiles, including age, sex, civil status, family structure, number of children and dependents, salary details, liabilities, health status, education level, years of service, rank, ancillary roles, and involvement in civic and religious organizations, as well as work and non-work-related recognitions. The second section evaluates the teachers' state of spirituality using a modified version of the spirituality scale by Delaney (2003), assessing their level of agreement or disagreement with various statements. The third section measures the teachers' degree of happiness using the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire, which includes 17 positive and 12 negative statements (scored inversely). Part I of the questionnaire, an addition to the standardized tool, was

pilot tested for face and content validity with 20 Junior High School Teachers from Campao Oriental High School, who did not participate in the main study.

Data Gathering Procedure

After reviewing the instruments to ensure they aligned with the study's objectives, the researcher obtained permission from the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principals to conduct the study. Permission was also sought from Junior High School teachers to allocate time for completing and discussing the survey questionnaire. The teachers were given adequate time to respond before the questionnaires were collected.

Prior to distribution, the questionnaire underwent a pilot test to enhance its validity and its reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. Responses were then encoded, tallied, and tabulated, and all data were carefully analyzed and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical tools were used to come up with an appropriate interpretation of data.

1. The profile of the teachers were summarized using percentages which is computed as follows:

$$P = \frac{f}{n}, f = \text{frequency counts}$$

Where:

P = Percentage

f = Frequency of the responses

n = Number of Cases

2. The teachers' degree of happiness was treated through weighted mean with the formula as follows:

$$x = \sum_i \frac{f(x_i)}{f}$$

where f is the frequency and x_i is the i th likert scale point.

The following Descriptive Interpretation was used.

1.00-1.85 – Not happy

1.86-2.71 – Somewhat unhappy

2.72-3.58 – Not particularly happy or unhappy

3.59-4.44 – Somewhat happy or moderately happy

4.45-5.30 – Rather happy or pretty happy

5.40-6.20 – Very happy

6.30-7.00 – Too happy

3. To determine whether teacher's profile is a significant predictor of happiness, multiple regression was used.

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4$$

Where:

Y = the dependent variable

X's = the p explanatory variables; and

b's = the regression coefficients

RESULTS

This chapter presents the findings, analysis, and interpretation of the data relevant to the study, addressing the specific objectives. The first section provides a detailed overview of the socio-demographic and spiritual profiles of Junior High School teachers in the 2nd Congressional District of Bohol. The second section assesses the teachers' level of happiness. The third section examines which aspects of the identified teacher profiles are significant predictors of happiness.

Table 1.1
Socio – economic Profile of Teacher - Respondents
N = 541

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21 - 25	94	17.4
26 - 30	149	27.5
31 - 35	103	19.0
36 - 40	93	17.2
41 - 45	51	9.4
46 - 50	12	2.2
51 - 55	33	6.1
56 - 60	4	0.7
61 - 65	2	0.4
Total	541	100
Sex		
Male	118	21.8
Female	423	78.2
Total	541	100

Civil Status		
Single	196	36.2
Separated	13	2.4
Married	324	59.9
Widowed	8	1.5
Total	541	100

Family Structure		
Living with immediate family	400	24.8
Living with extended family	141	75.2
Total	541	100

Number of Children		
0 - 1	344	63.6
2 - 3	149	27.5
4 - 5	37	6.8
6 - 7	9	1.7
8 - 9	2	0.4
Total	541	100

Number of Dependents		
0 - 1	308	56.9
2 - 3	186	34.4
4 - 5	36	6.7
6 - 7	11	2.0
Total	541	100

Gross Monthly Salary		
₱ 20,179.00 – ₱ 22, 148.00	300	55.5
₱ 22,149.00 – ₱ 24,223.00	41	7.6
₱ 24,224.00 – ₱ 26,746.00	184	34.0
₱ 38, 085.00 – ₱ 42,098.00	16	3.0
Total	541	100

Net Take Home Pay		
₱ 5,000.00 – ₱ 9,999.00	215	39.7
₱ 10,000.00 – ₱ 14,999.00	123	22.7
₱ 15,000.00 – ₱ 19,999.00	158	29.2
₱ 20,000.00 – ₱ 24,999.00	31	5.7
₱ 30,000.00 – ₱ 34,999.00	11	2.0
₱ 35,000.00 – ₱ 39,999.00	3	0.6
Total	541	100

Other Sources of Income		
0	236	43.6
1	272	50.3
2	33	6.1
Total	541	100
Number of Liabilities		
0	40	7.4
1	326	60.3
2	150	27.7
3	23	4.3
4	2	0.4
Total	541	100
Health Status		
0	499	92.2
1	40	7.4
2	2	0.4
Total	541	100

Table 1.1 presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, civil status, family structure/type, number of children, number of dependents, gross monthly salary, net take-home pay, other sources of income, liabilities, and health status.

Age. The largest age group among the respondents was 26-30 years old, with 149 (27.5%) teachers. This was followed by the 31-35 age group with 103 (19.0%), and the smallest group was 61-65 years old, with only 2 (0.4%). This indicates that most respondents are millennials, who are known for being tech-savvy, family-oriented, and achievement-focused (Levine, 2014).

Sex. The majority of respondents were female (78.2%) compared to male (21.8%). This aligns with data suggesting that teaching is predominantly a female profession, often linked with traditional gender roles (Ullah et al., 2016).

Civil Status. The majority of respondents were married (324, 59.9%), with fewer being single (196, 36.2%), separated (13, 2.4%), or widowed (8, 1.5%). This distribution reflects that most teachers are past the average marrying age, which is 26 for females and 28 for males (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2016).

Family Structure/Type. Most respondents (75.2%) lived with their immediate family, while 24.8% lived with extended family members.

Number of Children. The majority (63.6%) of respondents had 0-1 child, with only 0.4% having 8-9 children. This distribution mirrors the civil status data and global trends of decreasing birth rates, where many plan to have fewer children than previous generations.

Number of Dependents. A majority of respondents (56.9%) reported having 0-1 dependent. This finding is consistent with the family structure and number of children data.

Gross Monthly Salary. Most teachers (55.5%) had a gross monthly salary between ₱20,179.00 and ₱22,148.00. This range is typical for the dominant age group (26-30 years old) and positions held by the respondents, in compliance with R.A. No. 4670, which standardizes teacher salaries.

Net Take-Home Pay. The majority (39.7%) of respondents received a net monthly income between ₱5,000.00 and ₱9,999.00, while only 3 (0.6%) had a net income between ₱35,000.00 and ₱39,999.00. This is in line with Division Office Memorandum 05, S. 2018, which mandates a minimum net take-home pay of ₱5,000.00 for Department of Education personnel.

Number of Other Sources of Income. Most respondents (50.3%) had one additional source of income besides their salary. Only 6.1% had two other sources, likely due to many respondents being married and receiving additional support from their spouses.

Number of Liabilities. A majority of respondents (60.3%) reported having one liability, with a small minority (0.4%) having up to four liabilities.

Health Status. Most respondents (92.2%) reported no chronic or serious illness. The remaining respondents included 28 (5.2%) with chronic diseases, 16 (3.0%) with serious diseases, and fewer with both chronic and serious illnesses.

Table 1.2 displays the profile of the respondents in terms of professional profile, spiritually; highest educational attainment, number of years in service, present rank, number of ancillary designations, number of involvement in civic organizations, number of work-related recognitions, number of involvement in religious organizations, involvement in religious/ spiritual activities and number of involvement/ role in the local church.

Highest Educational Attainment. Data reveals that most (54.5%) of the teacher – respondents have Baccalaureate Degree with Masteral Units. Finding implies that majority of the respondents were taking their Master’s studies by the time the study was conducted. Postgraduate studies are widely thought to help teachers grow personally and professionally and be more effective and efficient facilitators of the teaching-learning process.

Number of Years in Service. The data shows that teachers with an experience of 3 years below has the highest frequency of 209 (38.6%), followed by 4 – 7 years (32.2%).

Table 1.2
Professional Profile of Teachers - Respondent
N = 541

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Baccalaureate Degree	152	28.1
Baccalaureate Degree with MA Units	295	54.5
Master's degree	75	13.9
Master's degree with Doctoral Units	12	2.2
Doctoral Degree	7	1.3
Total	541	100

Number of Years in Service		
3 years below	209	38.6
4 – 7	174	32.2
8 – 11	59	10.9
12 – 15	44	8.1
16 – 19	22	4.1
20 – 23	19	3.5
24 – 27	13	2.4
32 – 35	1	.2
Total	541	100

Present Rank / Position		
T – 1	300	55.5
T – 2	41	7.6
T – 3	184	34.0
MT – 1	16	3.0
Total	541	100

Number of Ancillary Designations		
1	120	22.2
2	280	51.8
3	132	24.4
4	9	1.7
Total	541	100

Number of Involvement in Civic Organizations		
0	432	79.9
1	63	11.6
2	43	7.9
3	2	0.4
4	1	0.2
Total	541	100

Number of Work – Related Recognitions

0	415	76.7
1	65	12.0
2	61	11.3
Total	541	100

Number of Non – Work Related Recognitions

0	510	94.3
1	19	3.5
2	7	1.3
3	3	0.6
4	2	0.4
Total	541	100

Number of Involvement in Religious Organizations

0	326	60.3
1	119	22.0
2	90	16.6
3	4	0.7
4	2	0.4
Total	541	100

Number of Involvement in Religious / Spiritual Activities

0	337	62.3
1	96	17.7
2	102	18.9
3	3	0.6
4	3	0.6
Total	541	100

Number of Involvement/ Role in Local Church

0	289	53.4
1	192	35.5
2	55	10.2
3	4	0.7
4	1	0.2
Total	541	100

Present Rank/ Position. A big fraction of the teacher-respondents (55.5%) hold Teacher I position, while only 16 (3.0%) have reached Master Teacher I position. This could be because most entrants of the teaching position are younger teachers and getting into higher positions like the Master Teacher position entails a lot of requirements including rich educational and training backgrounds and a lengthier teaching experience.

Number of Ancillary Designations. Majority (51.8%) of the teachers were having 2 ancillary designations. On the other hand, there is a notably lower number of teachers having 4 or more ancillary designations (1.7%). According to Khelai (2006), all studies show positive shifts of work occurring in the middle years, particularly between ages 40 and 50. Coupled with that, teachers usually find themselves with increased responsibilities and just as much, if not more, to do.

Number of Involvement in Civic Organizations. Majority of the teachers 432 (79.9%) were not involved in any civic affiliation, compared to only 11.6% having one civic affiliation and 0.2% having 4 civic affiliations. This is reflective of the findings of Carson, et. al (1975) which states that social participation experiences and aspirations with respect to educational activities and community life are limited for most teachers in three ways: (a) teachers believe their wide participation in such activities is inappropriate, (b) they have not participated extensively in these activities, and (c) they do not aspire toward a powerful decision-making role either in education or in community life.

Number of Work- Related Recognitions. Most of the respondents have not yet received any work- related recognitions (415 or 76.5%), while the least number of respondents (61, or 11.3%) had at most 2 work-related recognitions received. This may be because the teacher-respondents were mostly new in their respective institutions, and they are less likely to receive a lot of work-related recognitions because of the small span of time they had been in the profession.

Number of Non- Work-Related Recognitions. The data indicates that there were 510 (94.3%) who have not received any non- work-related recognitions and only 2 (.04%) who have received 4 non-work-related recognitions. This is reflective of the findings of Twenge et al (2012) which concluded that millennials' social traits are more of the 'Generation Me' in which their civic orientation and concern for others declined slightly. Millennials slowed, though did not reverse, trends toward reduced community feeling begun by the previous generation.

Number of Involvement in Religious Organizations. The result shows that most (60.3%) of the teachers did not have any religious affiliation and only 2 (0.4%) had 4 religious' affiliations. Religious affiliation pertains to teachers' membership or involvement in different religious organizations. The above-mentioned findings are in consonance with the other findings of this study showing teachers' sparse involvement in either work or non-work-related organizations.

Number of Involvement in Religious/ Spiritual Activities. Majority (62.3%) of the teachers were not involved in any religious/ spiritual activities compared to only 102

(18.9%) with 2 religious activity involvement. The least were those who have 3 (0.6%) and 4 (0.6%) religious/ spiritual activity involvements.

Number of involvement/ Role in Local Church. It is shown in the data that teachers who have no role in local church dominated at 289 (53.4%) while the least (0.2%) claimed to have 4 roles in the local church.

Table 1.3
State of Spirituality of the Teachers
N= 541

Statements	Frequency						WMS
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Intrapersonal							
1. I find meaning in my life experiences.	196	130	47	83	79	6	4.49
2. I have a sense of purpose.	167	154	32	91	93	4	4.37
3. I am happy about the person I have become.	183	142	29	106	77	4	4.44
4. I see the importance in everyday life.	207	171	31	89	43	0	4.76
5. My life is a process of becoming.	141	256	40	82	22	0	4.76
6. I use silence to get in touch with myself.	152	217	35	115	18	4	4.66
7. I feel thankful for my blessings.	271	123	2	25	60	60	4.63
8. I strive to correct the excesses in my own lifestyle patterns/practices.	152	226	35	109	16	3	4.70
9. I feel God's love for me directly.	276	149	7	49	24	36	4.92
Average Weighted Mean							4.64
Interpersonal							
10. I live in harmony with other people.	153	191	45	107	42	3	4.55
11. I value maintaining and nurturing my relationships with others.	242	224	20	40	14	1	5.18
12. I am able to receive love from others	201	242	15	64	16	3	5.00
13. I respect diversity of people.	216	230	19	60	13	3	5.05
14. I find happiness in teaching with my students.	274	154	9	47	12	45	4.92
15. I feel God's love for me through others.	236	181	6	57	26	35	4.81
16. I feel a selfless caring for others.	149	160	32	103	68	29	4.24
17. I accept others even when they do things that I think are wrong.	115	133	65	114	94	20	4.00
Average Weighted Mean							4.72

Transpersonal							
18. I read and meditate on God's word daily.	106	210	100	95	30	0	4.49
19. I believe in the existence of God.	245	184	30	70	8	4	5.06
20. My faith in God helps me cope during challenges in my life.	149	196	57	10 8	31	0	4.60
21. I believe that all living creatures deserve respect.	290	179	19	40	10	3	5.28
22. The earth is sacred.	277	193	18	39	10	4	5.25
23. I believe that nature should be respected.	275	198	15	37	15	1	5.25
24. I am actively involved in evangelism/missions.	253	182	23	64	12	7	5.07
25. My spirituality gives me my inner strength.	253	200	17	54	14	3	5.14
26. Prayer and meditation gives me a fresh break from the tiresome routine of my workplace.	268	194	21	44	11	3	5.21
27. Prayer is an integral part of my spiritual nature.	232	195	12	26	15	61	4.78
28. At times, I feel at one with the universe.	153	182	52	12 4	9	21	4.52
29. I always take time to assess my life choices as a way of living my spirituality.	157	213	36	10 7	8	20	4.64
30. I experience a connection of all life.	195	219	23	73	15	16	4.85
31. During worship, or at other times when connecting with God, I feel joy, which lifts me out of my daily concerns.	240	200	5	49	16	31	4.94
32. I find strength in my religion or spirituality.	235	158	16	56	32	44	4.70
33. I find comfort in my religion or spirituality.	216	166	15	67	37	40	4.62
34. I feel deep inner peace or harmony.	185	186	20	96	30	24	4.61
35. I ask for God's help in the midst of daily activities.	276	147	9	48	21	40	4.90
36. I am spiritually touched by the beauty of creation.	235	170	7	43	60	26	4.74
37. I desire to be closer to God or in union with Him.	236	58	3	39	109	96	3.97
Average Weighted Mean							4.83
Overall WMS Ave		Very High Spirituality					4.73

Scale:

- 1.00–1.83 – Very Low Spirituality
- 1.84–2.67 – Low Spirituality
- 2.68–3.51 – Moderate Spirituality
- 3.52–4.35 – High Spirituality
- 4.36–5.19 – Very High Spirituality
- 5.20–6.00 – Excellent Spirituality

Table 1. 3 shows the spirituality level of the respondents. The table indicates that the teachers generally have very high spirituality considering its overall mean of 4.73.

In particular, teacher's transpersonal spirituality had the highest mean (4.83) among the three aspects of spirituality. Items under transpersonal spirituality pertains to teachers' faith in God and a sense of deep connection and understanding of the purpose of her existence. A 'very high' transpersonal spirituality therefore means that teachers have a firmly established personal connection to God as a Supreme Being.

Pulchaski et al. (2009) contends that spirituality is the aspect of humanity that refers to the way individuals seek and express meaning and purpose and the way they experience their connectedness to the moment, to self, to others, to nature, and to the significant or sacred.

Filipinos are known for having a deep sense of spirituality (Yabut, 2018). The fatalistic mentality *bahala na*, although interchangeably used in different and wrong contexts, stems from Filipinos' deep sense of faith to a Supreme Being whom they perceive to be an all-knowing, ever-unfailing source of redemption when the rest of their human efforts fail.

Table 2
Teachers' Degree of Happiness
N = 541

Statements	Frequency						WMS
	6	5	4	3	2	1	
1. I don't feel particularly pleased with the way I am.	163	110	103	114	43	8	4.39
2. I am intensely interested in other people.	33	149	172	85	56	46	3.78
3. I feel that life is very rewarding.	264	190	66	6	7	8	5.25
4. I have very warm feelings towards almost everyone.	64	258	167	38	10	4	4.58
5. I rarely wake up feeling rested.	90	283	121	25	13	9	4.71
6. I am not particularly optimistic about the future.	164	112	90	102	57	16	4.33
7. I find most things amusing.	91	201	179	51	15	4	4.54
8. I am always committed and involved.	71	270	160	27	9	4	4.66
9. Life is good.	343	119	29	17	12	21	5.30
10. I do not think that the world is a good place.	288	80	53	54	35	31	4.81
11. I laugh a lot.	86	231	123	49	31	21	4.42
12. I am well satisfied about everything in my life.	146	222	125	30	14	4	4.82
13. I don't think I look attractive.	75	89	159	118	60	40	3.78
14. There is a gap between what I would like to do and what I have done.	28	101	205	129	65	13	3.74
15. I am very happy with my profession.	98	296	108	35	3	1	4.83
16. I find beauty in some things.	126	290	99	10	15	1	4.92
17. I always have a cheerful effect on others.	46	252	189	33	18	3	4.49
18. I can fit in (find time for) everything I want to.	39	200	205	71	23	3	4.28
19. I feel that I am not especially in control of my life.	127	124	130	79	64	17	4.22
20. I feel able to take anything on.	38	198	214	58	23	10	4.26
21. I feel fully mentally alert.	92	252	140	43	7	7	4.66
22. I often experience joy and elation.	65	211	168	41	33	23	4.30
23. I don't find it easy to make decisions.	76	173	162	88	35	7	4.27
24. I don't have a particular sense of meaning and purpose in my life.	43	288	155	29	10	16	4.51
25. I feel I have a great deal of energy.	44	218	180	49	35	15	4.26
26. I usually have a good influence on events.	29	186	194	75	39	18	4.07
27. I don't have fun with other people.	191	201	77	57	9	6	4.91
28. I don't feel particularly healthy.	355	112	10	21	8	35	5.26
29. I don't have particularly happy memories of the past.	114	74	135	65	90	63	3.76

WMS Average	Rather happy or pretty happy	4.49
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Scale:

- 1.00-1.85 – Not happy
- 1.86-2.71 – Somewhat unhappy
- 2.72-3.58 – Not particularly happy or unhappy
- 3.59-4.44 – Somewhat happy or moderately happy
- 4.45-5.30 – Rather happy or pretty happy
- 5.40-6.20 – Very happy
- 6.30-7.00 – Too happy

Table 2 shows the degree of happiness of the respondents. The overall weighted mean of 4.49 means that the respondents are “rather happy or pretty happy”.

Panda & Mohanty (2003) emphasizes that happiness among teachers is an important element in the educational system since the presence of happy teachers will help in creating a happy society through nurturing the next generation appropriately.

On a general note, it can be convincingly stated that young people are extremely cheerful as they have passion towards life and the curiosity, desire and of course, hope of living every moment that life has to offer.

It is interesting to note that of all items in the happiness survey, the item that earned the highest mean score (5.30) is item number 9, “Life is good”. It means that teachers’ overall perception of life is good. The statement itself may be a reflection of their disposition about life in general.

On the other hand, item number 14 “There is a gap between what I would like to do and what I have done.” got the lowest mean of 3.74. This may imply teachers’ frustrations over the things that they want to do or pursue in their lives and the limited time and resources that teachers have in order to pursue these wants.

Table 3
Multiple Regression Analysis on Teachers’ Profile and Happiness

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
1	(Constant)	3.765	.369	10.212	.000
	Age	-.015	.007	-2.228	.026
	Sex	-.015	.076	.202	.840
	Family Structure	.152	.066	2.308	.021
	Number of Children	-.004	.035	-.111	.911
	Number of Dependents	-.004	.031	-.115	.909
	Gross Monthly Salary	.006	.000	-.589	.556
	Net Take Home Pay	.056	.000	-.576	.565

Other Sources of Income	-.009	.052	-.176	.861
Liabilities	.005	.046	.107	.915
Health Status	.103	.112	.920	.358
Highest Educational Attainment	.022	.040	.548	.584
Number of years in service	.024	.010	2.375	.018
Present rank/position	.022	.049	.438	.662
Number of Ancillary	.023	.039	.585	.559
Number of involvements in Civil Organization	.051	.052	.964	.335
Number of Work-Related Number of Recognitions	.032	.049	.661	.509
Number of Non-Work-Related Recognitions	-.019	.068	-.285	.775
Religious Organization	-.087	.049	-1.772	.077
Religious/Spiritual Activities	.000	.048	.005	.996
Number of Involvement /Role of Local Church	.036	.051	.708	.479
Civil Status	.014	.074	.192	.848
Overall Spirituality	.240	.040	5.921	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Happiness

Table 3 shows the results of a multiple linear regression which was used to determine whether teacher profile can predict teachers' happiness. A significant regression equation was found ($F(22,518) = 2.666, 0 < .000^b$) with an R^2 of .102. Participants' predicted happiness is equal to $-0.026(\text{Age}) + 0.021(\text{Family Structure}) + 0.018(\text{Numbers of Years in Service}) + 0.000(\text{Overall Spirituality})$ where family structure is coded 1= living with immediate family, 2= living with extended family; number of years in service; the state of spirituality is coded as 1=very good spirituality, 2=poor spirituality, 3=fair spirituality, 4=good spirituality, 5=very good spirituality and 6=excellent spirituality.

Of the teacher profiles identified, age, family structure, years in service and spirituality are found to be significant predictors of teachers' happiness.

Anchored on the results, a teacher's happiness will decrease by 0.026 for every level increase of her age, holding all other variables constant. Meanwhile, there is a 0.018 increase in teacher's happiness for every unit increase in her number of years in service and an increase of 0.021 if she is living with her extended family, still while holding all other variables constant. There is also an increase in spirituality - each while holding all other variables constant.

Bluntly, the results indicate that the older a teacher gets, the less happy she tends to be. This conforms to the statements of Twenge, Sherman and Lyubmorky (2015) that as people grow older, it is believed that life begins to take a new shape, priorities change amazingly and the dreading issues of midlife crisis followed by old age tends to lower happiness levels.

However, it also shows that the longer the teacher has been in service, the more people she stays with at home, and the higher her spirituality is - the happier she becomes.

DISCUSSION

Findings

Based on the analysis of the data, the following findings were drawn which served as basis for conclusions and corresponding recommendations.

Profile of the Respondents. The respondents who participated in the study were mostly millennial teachers who belonged to the 26 – 30 years old age group. They were mostly married females who were living with their immediate family and who had at most one child or dependent at home.

With regards to their sources of income, more than half of the respondents have one additional income aside from their salary. With most of them earning a gross salary income of ₱ 20,179.00 – ₱ 24,000.00, results revealed that these teachers also have a predominant net monthly income of ₱ 5,000.00 - ₱ 9,999.00. As to the health condition of the respondents, majority of them were without illness/ disease.

They were mostly Baccalaureate Degree holders who were currently taking their Master's studies by the time this study was conducted and they had been in service for 3 – 7 years, mostly holding Teacher I position.

As to the number of ancillary designations, a bigger number of respondents have two ancillary designations and did not have any involvement in civic organizations.

As to work- related recognitions, since majority of the teachers are new to DepEd, most of them had not received any awards yet. Likewise, most of the respondents had not received any non-work-related recognition since they were mostly not involved in any organization. As to religious affiliation, more than half of the respondents did not have religious affiliations, and were not holding any role in their local church.

The Teachers' Degree of Happiness. The teachers were found to be rather happy or pretty happy.

Teachers' Profile as Predictor of Happiness. Of the teachers' identified profile, the predictors of their happiness are their age, structure of the family, years in service and state of spirituality.

Conclusions

The study concludes that happier teachers are those with longer teaching experience and with higher spirituality. Furthermore, a teacher tends to be happier if

he/she is living with his/her immediate family. Lastly, the study also concludes that teachers seem to be less happy as they advance in age.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were given.

1. The Department of Education should continue to maintain and promote existing programs that recognize teachers' tenure to encourage younger teachers to do better and remain in their service as length of service contributes to teachers' happiness.
2. Teachers should spend more time in nurturing her relationship with their own selves, with the people around them such as their extended family, and with God; as spirituality is essential in keeping teachers' happiness in tune.
3. Teachers should continue keeping a good balance between career and family life, and they should spend more time with their family as much as possible because the people they live with are elemental in keeping their happiness.
4. Researchers should pursue the same study, measuring the same construct in other congressional districts to see if the results are consistent with this research findings; or explore other predictors not covered in this study.
5. Future researchers may consider conducting a study on other predictors of happiness, especially those that are recreational in nature (taboo), or conduct a study on a combination of one or two factors. They may also look into qualitatively gauging other teacher profiles of happiness or looking for happiness scales that are tailor-fit to the nature and culture of the respondents being surveyed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Any ethical concerns that could have risen throughout the study were resolved by securing necessary permits. Also, the researcher personally handed the research tools to the schools, with the assistance of the administrators, which included the informed consent form and questionnaires. Before data collection began, all research terms and conditions were fully disclosed to maintain transparency. Despite receiving clearance from the school principals and administrators, the researcher obtained informed consent from participants by individually requesting them to participate and providing thorough information about the study, including potential risks and benefits, as well as privacy safeguards. Each participant was asked to review and sign the informed consent form, indicating their comprehension and willingness to be involved in the study. It was optional to provide the participants' names, which were coded to preserve their identity. To safeguard data, further confidentiality measures were put in place, such as limiting access to physical and electronic resources. The study closely followed data privacy and research ethics guidelines, and participants were made aware of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment without facing consequences.

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